

Assessment of Effectiveness of Mass Media Usage in Promoting Agroforestry Technologies Among Smallholder Farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Agroforestry, which integrates trees and shrubs into crop and livestock systems, offers numerous benefits, including improved soil fertility, increased biodiversity, and enhanced resilience to climate change. This study assesses the effectiveness of mass media in promoting agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select 180 respondents. Kaduna State was first stratified into its three agricultural zones: Zone A (Maigana), Zone B (Barnawa), and Zone C (Samaru Kataf). One Local Government Area (LGA) was randomly selected from each zone, targeting those with the highest number of agroforestry farmers. Three districts were randomly chosen from each LGA, and two villages were purposively selected from each district, culminating in 18 villages. Finally, ten agroforestry farmers from each village were purposively selected, totalling 180 respondents. Data was collected using a validated and pretested structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, tables, percentages, and means were used for data analysis. Findings reveal that radio is the most effective medium for disseminating agricultural information, cited by 52.8% of respondents, followed by posters and mobile phones. However, significant constraints, including inconvenient programme timing, poor network services, lack of extension services, and economic barriers, hinder the effective use of mass media. The demographic analysis indicates that most respondents are within the productive age bracket of 31-40 years, predominantly male, with varying educational attainment and farming experience. The study recommends enhancing radio programme scheduling, improving network infrastructure, strengthening extension services, among others to overcome these challenges.

Keywords: Agroforestry, Adoption, Mass media, Smallholder Farmers. Technologies,

1.0 Introduction

Agroforestry is a collective term for land use systems and technologies in which woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboo, etc.) are intentionally used on the same land management

units as agricultural crops and/or animals in some spatial arrangement or temporal sequence. In agroforestry systems there are both ecological and economic interactions between the different components. Agroforestry has been an essential aspect of agriculture [1]. [2] maintain that it can

be a spatial arrangement of plants and animals with simultaneous forest integration or a time-sequence where trees and shrubs are planted on a fallow to improve fertility. Agroforestry has long been associated with sustainable livelihoods, sound land management, and long-term growth.

Diffusion of innovation refers to the spread of new ideas from the source of invention or creation to its ultimate users or adopters [3;4]. [4] states that the sources of information for farmers include mass media, neighbours, friends, relatives, government agricultural agencies, salesmen, and dealers. In addition, he ranks the order of information sources on awareness of agricultural information, beginning with the mass media, friends and neighbours, agricultural agencies, dealers, and salesmen.

The media system, technologies, and techniques supporting it evolved alongside society's increasing population, needs, and complexities, including the agricultural sector. With the potency and capacity to provide vital knowledge to farmers and impact behaviour positively, the modern media can be exploited for its potency and effectiveness in providing information to farmers [5]. Innovation is key to improving food and agriculture productivity, sustainability, and resilience. An agricultural innovation system is about people, the knowledge, technology, infrastructure, and cultures that have created or learned who they work with and what new ideas they are experimenting with [6]. Hence, there is a need to extend such innovations almost immediately to farmers using mass media channels in an effective, timely, and impactful manner [7]. Agroforestry is an activity that differs from conventional crop farming and agro-processing, hence the need for information on how to utilise land in crop production, tree farming, and pasture [8]. The mass media is a tool used by agricultural extension to enhance the adoption of new technologies in agriculture [9]. To get the message across as efficiently, effectively, and distinctly as possible to the intended audience, it is better to separate it from the noise and other information competing for their attention and give them information in a clear, simple, and vivid manner in the language they understand and prefer, to encourage them to take the intended positive action to accept, adopt and effectively utilise innovation to change their circumstance [10; 4; 11; 12; 13;3]. Successful agroforestry development is dependent upon the

design capability with percentage need as well as the use of the "right" structures, media, and messages for dissemination to encourage awareness and adoption of relevant technologies in agroforestry [14; 15; 15].

Agroforestry technologies cannot develop without an effective and robust utilisation of mass media resources and channels to promote best practices through effective information dissemination. There are observed gaps and inadequacies in the current agricultural information system used by extension services as it involves disseminating information to agroforestry farmers, which must be tackled effectively [16]. It is worth noting that improved extension systems have great potential for providing farmers with more and better information through mass media channels [17]. A successful extension system must constantly assess the impact of its information delivery system on farmers. Information is critical to success in the rural agricultural sector [4]. How information is packaged, disseminated, and perceived by the intended user significantly affects whether an innovation is accepted or rejected [18].

Smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria, face significant challenges in adopting and implementing agroforestry technologies. That could enhance their agricultural productivity and sustainability. Agroforestry, the integration of trees and shrubs with crops and livestock, has been shown to have numerous benefits. Such as improved soil fertility, increased biodiversity, and diversified income sources [1]. However, the uptake of agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in the State remains low. One of the key factors contributing to the limited adoption of agroforestry technologies is the ineffective dissemination of information and the lack of awareness among farmers. Traditional extension services and interpersonal communication channels have often been insufficient. In reaching and educating many smallholder farmers, particularly those in remote rural areas. In this regard, mass media, such as radio, television, and print media, could potentially play a crucial role in promoting agroforestry technologies and increasing their adoption among smallholder farmers.

While existing studies have extensively examined the role of mass media in disseminating agricultural information. There is a noticeable gap in research explicitly focusing on the effectiveness of mass media in promoting agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Most studies [18; 19] have generally addressed agricultural information dissemination without isolating agroforestry practices' unique aspects and requirements. Additionally, while some research has highlighted the general effectiveness of radio and digital media in agricultural extension [20; 21], there is limited empirical data on the comparative impact of various mass media channels specifically tailored to agroforestry information.

Furthermore, demographic factors such as age, gender, and educational level have been identified as influential in the adoption of agricultural technologies [22; 23], but there is a lack of detailed studies on how these factors interact with mass media usage to promote agroforestry practices. The infrastructural and economic barriers to effective media usage, such as poor network services and the cost of mobile data, have been noted [24], yet there is insufficient research on specific interventions to overcome these challenges within the context of agroforestry.

Moreover, while digital media's role in real-time and interactive information dissemination has been recognised [25], its potential in promoting agroforestry technologies remains underexplored, particularly in how it can be integrated with traditional media to maximise reach and effectiveness. Addressing these gaps can provide more comprehensive strategies for enhancing the adoption of agroforestry technologies and contribute to sustainable agricultural development in Kaduna State and similar States.

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of mass media usage in promoting agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. It investigated farmers' current utilisation of mass media channels, the extent to which mass media influences their awareness and adoption of agroforestry technologies, and the factors that facilitate or hinder the effectiveness of mass media in this context. The findings of this study will provide

valuable insights for policymakers, extension services, and development organisations to develop more targeted and effective strategies for promoting agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Against this background, this research seeks to achieve the following stated objectives.

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents;
- ii. identify the effectiveness of primary sources of mass media used;
- iii. examine the respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of mass media in promoting the adoption of agroforestry technologies and
- iv. assess the constraints to the effective use of mass media in promoting agroforestry technologies.

The hypothesis is stated in a null form thus;

H₀: The use of mass media is ineffective in promoting agroforestry technologies among the farmers in the study area.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Description of the study area

The study was carried out in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The State is between latitude 09⁰ and 11⁰ N and longitude 06⁰ and 09⁰ E. It has a land mass area of about 46,053 km² and a projected population of 8,977,855.26 as of 2020, based on the Kaduna Population Dynamics Report by Kaduna Business School (KDBS) [26]. Katsina and Kano State border Kaduna state to the North; Bauchi to the East; Plateau to the South-East, Niger to the West and Abuja to the South. The mean annual rainfall decreases from south to north (1152 mm- 635 mm). The State is divided into three senatorial zones: Kaduna North, Central, and South. It comprises twenty-three (23) Local Government Areas 46 Local Development Areas (LDAs), and there are 255 political wards [27].

2.2 Sampling technique

A multi-stage sample technique was used to select 180 respondents. The first stage was stratifying Kaduna state along the three existing agricultural zones. The three agricultural Zones are Zone A (Maigana), Zone B (Barnawa), and Zone C (SamaruKataf). The second stage involved simple random selection of one (1) LGA

from the three (3) Agricultural Zones. Three (3) Local government areas were selected for the study. The LGAs that were chosen were those with the highest number of agroforestry farmers in each agricultural zone in three (3) agricultural zones of Kaduna state, Nigeria. The third stage was a simple random selection of three (3) districts from each of the three (3) LGAs selected earlier to give nine districts. The fourth stage was a purposive selection of two (2) villages from each of the nine districts to give eighteen villages in all. The last stage was a purposive selection of ten (10) agroforestry farmers from each rural community, totalling 180 respondents as a sample size. Data was collected through a validated and pretested structured questionnaire. Both open and closed-ended questions were designed to meet the study's objectives. A total of one hundred and eighty (180) questionnaires were administered for the study, with sixty (60) administered for each of the three (3) LGAs selected. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, tables, percentages, and mean were used to analyse the data.

2.3 Measurement of variables

Variables like effectiveness were measured on a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from very effective (5), effective (4), undecided (3), less effective (2), and ineffective (1). Perceptions were measured on a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). Mean $1+2+3+4+5=15 \div 5=3$ was used as a benchmark to rate respondents' perceptions into positive/indifferent/negative, respectively. Constraints were measured on a 5-point Likert scale that ranges from very severe (5), severe (4), undecided (3), less severe (2), and not severe (1); effective index and Chi-square were employed for the analysis.

Chi-Square Mathematical model:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum (F_0 - F_e)^2}{F_e} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where;

χ^2 = Chi – square calculated

\sum = Summation sign

F_0 = Observed frequencies

F_e = Expected Frequencies

3.0 Results

3.1 Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

The results presented in Table 1 show that many (58.3%) of the respondents were between 31 and 40 years old. Also, about (17.8%) of the respondents were between 21 and 30 years old and (9.4%) were between 41 and 50 years old while (9.4%) were between 51 and 60 years old. The table below further shows that a significant number (32.8%) of the population had between 6 and 10 members in their household. Moreso, many (20.0%) of the respondents had between 16 and 20 members per household and a significant proportion (19.4%) of the respondents had between 1 and 5 members per household. The table below also reveals that many (28.3%) of respondents had between 1 and 5 years of farming experience, while (22.8) had 6 and 10 years' experience in agriculture. Also, about (20.0%) had 21 and 25 years' experience in farming. The results further showed that many (34.4%) of the respondents had between 6 and 10 hectares of land for their farming activities, (22.8%) of the respondents had between 0.5 and 5 hectares of land. About (18.3%) had between 11 and 15 hectares of land for farming purposes and (15.0%) of the respondents had between 16 and 20 hectares of land and a few (3.9%) of the respondents had above 25 hectares of land.

Table 1 Socio-economic Characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age (Years)		
21 – 30	32	17.8
31 – 40	105	58.3
41 – 50	17	9.4
51- 60	15	8.3
61- Above	11	6.1
Total	180	100.0
Household Size		
1-5	35	19.4
6-10	59	32.8
11-15	32	17.8
16- 20	36	20.0
Above 20	18	10.0
Total	180	100
Farming Experience (Years)		
1 – 5	51	28.3
6 – 10	41	22.8
11 – 15	21	11.7
16 – 20	28	15.6
21 – 25	36	20
Total	180	100
Farm Size (Ha)		
0.5 – 5	41	22.8
6 – 10	62	34.4
11 – 15	33	18.3
16 – 20	28	15.6
21 – 25	9	5.0
Above 25	7	3.9
Total	180	100

Source: Field survey, 2019.

Evidence presented in Figure 1 revealed that many (70.6%) of the respondents were male and only (29.4%) were female and it shows a

significant gender disparity in the farming community in the study area.

Fig.1. Distribution of respondents according to their sex

Entries presented in Figure 2 showed the distribution of the respondents according to their marital status. The fig revealed a larger proportion (61.7%) of the respondents were married, about (19.4%) were single, (8.3%) were

divorced and (7.8%) of the population were widows/widowers. It an indication that most of the respondents were married and still living together.

Fig. 2: Distribution of respondents according to their marital status

Data presented in Figure 3 revealed distribution of the respondents according to their educational attainment. The figure showed that a significant proportion (37.8%) of respondents had acquire education up to secondary education level, (25.0%) had education up tertiary level and (17.8%) of the respondents had education up to

primary school level. About (11.1%) of respondents had Quranic education and only a few (6.7%) of the respondents had adult education. It is clear indication that almost all the respondents had acquired one form of education or the other.

Fig. 3: Distribution of respondents according to their level of education

3.2 Effectiveness of primary sources of mass media used by the respondents

disseminating agricultural information (52.8%), followed by posters and mobile phones.

The results in Table 2 revealed that radio was perceived as the most effective medium for

Table 2: Major Source of Effective Agroforestry Technologies Information to Farmers through Mass Media Channel

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Levels of Effectiveness
Radio	95	52.8	Very effective
Print Materials (Posters)	42	23.3	Effective
Television	26	14.4	Undecided
Mobile phone	12	6.7	Less effective
Internet	05	2.8	Not effective
Total	180	100	

Source: Field survey, 2019

3.3 Respondent's perception of the effectiveness of mass media

Agroforestry technology, while posters, with a mean of (M=4.0), mobile phone (M=3.67), agricultural -shows (M=3.67), television (M=3.38), newspaper (M=3.38) and the Internet (M=3.25), respectively.

Evidence presented in Table 4 shows that the respondents perceived radio to be very effective, with a mean of (M=4.50), as strongly agreed in information dissemination in the adoption of

Table 3: Respondents' perception of the effectiveness of Mass Media in Agroforestry Technologies' information dissemination

Mass media	Strongly Agreed (5)	Agreed (4)	Undecided (3)	Disagreed (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)	Sum	Mean (x)	Remark
Mobile phone	43	71	38	19	9	660	3.67	Agreed
Posters	64	81	17	5	13	718	4.00	Agreed
Radio	132	26	11	7	4	810	4.50	S. Agreed
Television	52	98	-	21	6	700	3.38	Agreed
Newspaper	48	56	16	36	24	608	3.38	Agreed
Ext. Bulleting	41	66	18	15	40	593	3.29	Agreed
Internet	33	74	-	51	22	585	3.25	Agreed
Agric-shows	44	87	8	28	13	661	3.67	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2019

* Mean \geq 3.0 for decision rule.

3.4 Constraints to effective use of mass media in promoting agroforestry technologies

The results presented in Table 4 identifies several constraints affecting the effectiveness of mass media, including inconvenient timing of

programmes ($x = 3.45$); poor network services ($x = 3.41$); lack of extension services, low awareness of agroforestry benefits, limited capital, and high costs of mobile and internet.

Table 4: Constraints to effective mass media usage for promoting Agroforestry technologies

Constraints	Mean	Rank
Mass Media Programmes do not correspond with the convenient time of the farmers.	3.45	1
Poor network services for Mobile phones/ Internet	3.41	2
Limited capital/low-income level to procure farming tools	2.86	5
Government policies do not carry farmers along (Extension Services)	3.34	3
Low awareness of the potential of agroforestry	3.32	4
High cost of subscriber charges (Internet & Mobile Phones)	2.80	6

* Mean ≥ 3.0 denotes very severe

Source: Field Survey, 2019

3.5 Chi-square test results of the significance of the effectiveness of mass media

The findings presented in Table 5 provide essential insights into the effectiveness of mass media in disseminating information to promote the adoption of agroforestry technologies among farmers in the study area.

The chi-square test results indicate that the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected, as the calculated chi-square value of 80 is greater than the critical value of 53.5 at the 0.01 level of probability. This suggests that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of mass media and the dissemination of information to farmers.

Table 5: Chi-square test of significance on the effectiveness of mass media

Rating	Rank	f_0	$R+f_0$	Tot. _o	f_e	f_e-f_0	$(f_e-f_0)^2$	$(f_e-f_0)^2/f_e$	Tab-value@1%
Most effective	2	46	47	93	85.8	39.8	1584.0	18.5	
Effective	1	78	80	158	145.8	67.8	4596.8	31.5	
Undecided	4	14	17	31	28.6	14.6	213.2	7.5	
Less effective	3	32	36	68	62.8	30.8	948.6	15.1	
Not effective	5	10	15	25	23.1	13.1	171.6	7.4	
Total		180	195					80	53.5

Mass media is an effective medium for disseminating information at a 0.01 percent probability.

Source: Field Survey, 2019

4.0 Discussion

The results in Table 1 indicated that most respondents (58.8%) fall within the age bracket of 31-40 years, indicating a predominance of individuals in their productive working years. This age group is crucial for the adoption of new technologies due to their physical capabilities and willingness to innovate. Studies by [24] confirm that younger farmers are more likely to adopt new technologies, driven by their longer planning horizons and adaptability. [28] asserts that younger farmers are more receptive to agricultural innovations, making them prime candidates for adopting agroforestry practices. This finding falls within the age bracket of 16 - 64 years, defined by [29] as an economically productive population. Household size is a critical determinant of labour

availability in traditional agriculture. The study shows that most respondents have household sizes between 6-10 individuals (32.8%). Larger households can provide more labour for intensive farming activities like agroforestry. The result is in tandem with [30] highlights that household size directly impacts the availability of labour for agricultural production. Similarly, [31] emphasises that larger households have more labour resources, which is essential for the labour-intensive nature of agroforestry practices. Also, [32], posit that household size plays a vital role in agro-based entrepreneurial activities. The Table further reveals that a significant portion of respondents (28.3%) have 1-5 years of farming experience, with many having small to medium-sized farms (6-10 hectares). This aligns with the typical profile of smallholder farmers who are gradually scaling

up their operations. The result also agrees with [33] found similar patterns in farming experience among Nigerian farmers, suggesting a common trend in the region. Research by [33] supports the finding that smallholder farms in Nigeria typically range between 0.8 to 1.3 hectares, slightly smaller than the average found in this study.

[33] highlight that gender plays a significant role in information access and usage, affecting how agricultural information is disseminated and utilised. Figure 1 shows the respondents' distribution according to their gender. The study found that males constitute (70%) of the respondents, indicating a male-dominated agricultural sector. Gender influences access to information and the adoption of new technologies. [34] and [22] reported similar gender distributions, with men being more likely to engage in agricultural activities and adopt new technologies. Also, it was submitted that male respondents are more likely to adopt mass media in agroforestry technologies than their female counterparts [35]. Figure 2 further shows that many (61.0%) of the respondents were married, and the finding is in harmony with the findings of [22], who found that 59.38% of respondents in a similar study were married. It could be deduced that since the majority of the respondents in this study are married, they could source agroforestry technologies through the mass media to increase their productivity and boost their income. Also, figure 3 reveals that (98.4%) of the respondents were literate, which can enhance their thinking capacity and make informed decisions about adopting agroforestry technologies. Education levels among respondents influence their ability to access and comprehend information about agroforestry technologies. Educated farmers are more likely to adopt new practices. [37] found that education positively impacts the adoption of agricultural technologies. [36] underscores the need for information to be physically and intellectually accessible, emphasising the role of education in technology adoption.

The results in Table 3 highlight that radio is perceived as the most effective medium for disseminating agricultural information (52.8%), followed by posters and mobile phones. This study's result aligns with that of [22], supporting the finding that radio is a primary source of effective mass media for agroforestry information dissemination. Also, [21] asserts that radio is

crucial for reaching rural farmers due to its accessibility and broad reach.

Evidence presented in Table 4 shows that the respondents perceived radio to be very effective, with a mean of (M=4.50), as strongly agreed in information dissemination in the adoption of Agroforestry technology, while posters, with a mean of (M=4.0), mobile phone (M=3.67), agricultural -shows (M=3.67), television (M=3.38), newspaper (M=3.38) and the Internet (M=3.25), respectively. This suggests that the respondents strongly agree with the effectiveness of radio in this context. The existing literature supports the effectiveness of radio as a mass media channel in rural and agricultural development. Radio has been widely recognised as a powerful tool for information sharing and education in developing countries, particularly in rural areas where access to other media outlets may be limited [Lwoga & Stilwell, 38; Sabo, 39]. Radio has the advantage of reaching a broad audience, including those with low literacy levels, and it can effectively disseminate agricultural information, extension messages, and technology adoption recommendations [40;41]. The findings also indicate that posters, mobile phones, and agricultural shows were perceived as relatively effective, with mean scores ranging from 3.67 to 4.0. These media channels have also been documented in the literature as valuable for agricultural information dissemination and technology adoption. Posters can effectively convey visual information and serve as a tangible reference material for farmers [42].

On the other hand, mobile phones have become increasingly important in rural areas, enabling farmers to access timely information, receive advisory services, and connect with extension agents [43;44]. Agricultural shows and exhibitions provide an interactive platform for farmers to engage with researchers, extension workers, and other stakeholders, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and the promotion of new technologies [45;46]. In contrast, the respondents perceived television, newspapers, and the internet as less effective, with mean scores ranging from 3.25 to 3.38. This finding aligns with the literature, which suggests that these media channels may face challenges in reaching and engaging rural populations, particularly in areas with limited infrastructure, low literacy levels, and uneven access to technology [38; 40].

Overall, the results highlight the importance of understanding the preferences and perceptions of the target audience when designing and implementing communication strategies for agricultural development and technology adoption. Leveraging the most effective mass media channels, such as radio, can significantly enhance the reach and impact of information dissemination efforts in rural communities.

The results presented in Table 5 identifies several constraints affecting the effectiveness of mass media, including inconvenient timing of programmes ($x = 3.45$); poor network services ($x = 3.41$); lack of extension services, low awareness of agroforestry benefits, limited capital, and high costs of mobile and internet services.[47] discuss the impact of inadequate infrastructure and financial limitations on the effectiveness of mass media in agricultural extension. Also,[36] cites poverty as a significant barrier to information access, reflecting the economic constraints highlighted in the study.

The findings presented in Table 6 provide essential insights into the effectiveness of mass media in disseminating information to promote the adoption of agroforestry technologies among farmers in the study area.

The chi-square test results indicate that the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, as the calculated chi-square value of 80 is greater than the critical value of 53.5 at the 0.01 level of probability. This suggests that there is a statistically significant relationship between the use of mass media and the dissemination of information to farmers. The existing literature strongly supports the role of mass media in facilitating the adoption of agricultural technologies, including agroforestry practices. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of mass media channels in information dissemination and technology adoption in the agricultural sector. For instance, a survey by [45] found that mass media, such as radio, television, and print media, were important sources of information for farmers in Nigeria, influencing their adoption of agricultural innovations.

Similarly, [41] highlighted the potential of mobile phones and other ICT-based media to enhance the accessibility of agricultural information and improve farmer decision-making in developing countries. The authors noted that integrating mass

media with extension services and other communication channels can significantly improve information dissemination and technology adoption. Furthermore,[36] emphasised the importance of using mass media and interpersonal communication channels to effectively reach and engage farmers, especially in rural areas with limited access to information and communication technologies. The findings in the current study imply that mass media can be a powerful tool for disseminating information and promoting the adoption of agroforestry technologies among farmers in the study area. The significant relationship between mass media and information dissemination suggests that policymakers, extension agencies, and agricultural development programs should strategically leverage various mass media channels to reach and engage with farmers. By utilising a diverse range of mass media, such as radio, television, print media, and digital platforms, these stakeholders can effectively communicate information, recommendations, and best practices related to agroforestry technologies. This can help overcome barriers to information access, increase awareness, and ultimately enhance the adoption of these technologies among the target farming communities. Overall, the findings presented in Table 6 and the supporting literature highlight the importance of integrating mass media into comprehensive communication strategies for agricultural development and technology adoption, particularly in the context of agroforestry promotion.

5.0 Conclusion

The study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of mass media in promoting agroforestry technologies among smallholder farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that radio is the most effective medium for disseminating agricultural information, followed by posters and mobile phones. The study also highlights significant constraints, such as inconvenient timing of programmes, poor network services, lack of extension services, and economic barriers, which impede the effective use of mass media. Additionally, demographic factors, including age, gender, household size, and educational level, play crucial roles in the adoption of agroforestry technologies.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings emanating from the study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. **Enhancing Radio Programmes:** Given the high effectiveness of radio, it is recommended to increase the frequency and improve the timing of agricultural programmes to match farmers' schedules.
- ii. **Improving Network Services:** Investment in better network infrastructure is essential to enhance mobile and internet access in rural areas.
- iii. **Strengthening Extension Services:** There is a need for more extension workers to provide guidance and support to farmers, facilitating the adoption of agroforestry technologies.
- iv. **Increasing Awareness:** Educational campaigns should be launched to raise awareness about the benefits of agroforestry, targeting both male and female farmers.
- v. **Financial Support:** Providing financial assistance and affordable credit facilities can help farmers overcome economic barriers to adopting new technologies.

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8.0 Conflict of interest

We declared that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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